
Research Article

Effects of Drying Methods, Fermentation Times and Containers on pH and Some Functional Properties of Processed Locust Beans (*Parkia biglobosa*)

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Abstract

Cleaned Locust bean seeds were dehulled, cooked at 110°C and steamed at 45°C, then fermented using different containers of calabash, stainless steel and plastic at different fermentation times of 24, 48 and 72 hours. The samples were dried using sun and oven drying methods (55°C) to state their effects on the pH and some functional properties which includes, bulk density (BD), water absorption capacity (WAC) and oil absorption capacity (OAC). The results obtained from the effect of using sundried samples are pH 6.40, bulk density 0.92, WAC 2.14, and OAC 1.30. Results for Oven dried samples are pH 5.6, bulk density 0.98, WAC 2.16 and OAC 1.26. For fermentation, time pH was between 5.54 and 6.41, bulk density was 0.91-0.97, WAC was 1.83-2.39, and OAC 1.17-1.44. Fermentation container recorded 5.85-6.20 for pH, bulk density 0.93-0.96, WAC 1.94-2.43, and OAC 1.17-1.44. The outcome from the results reflected pH increase with prolonged fermentation time. Furthermore, the level of pH was highest in containers that could retain heat and sustain enzymatic reactions in the order of calabash>plastic>stainless steel. Finally, moisture loss was significant in the oven dried (55°C) samples.

Key words: functional properties, drying, fermentation, time and container

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Introduction

Food for daily sustenance of living beings cannot be over emphasized, thus it is a key to life (Iheke *et al.*, 2017). The intakes of proper nutrients are essential for man's wellbeing. The Seeds pose high nutritive and calorific values which make them important in diets (Adeyeye and Fagbokun, 2005). Furthermore, food legumes or

pulses are found throughout the world with great varieties growing in the tropics and sub- tropics (Ihekeronye and Ngoddy, 1985). Food legumes offer a singular advantage of providing plant proteins with less difficulty of processing and yet higher prospects of boosting energy efficiency than that supplied via animal proteins (Balogun and Fetuga, 1986). Pulses are recognized and recommended for consumption for the noble purpose of neutralizing acids in the body systems (Russel- Seddon, 1985). Thus gearing efforts towards the effective utilization of these effective plant proteins for nutritional and functional properties cannot be over emphasized.

Figure 1: flow chart for the processing of Locust bean food condiment

Parkia biglobosa popularly known as African locust bean is a perennial deciduous tree legume and dicotyledonous angiosperm of fabaceae (leguminoseae) family, belonging to the sub family of minosodaea (Akande *et al.*, 2010). It is well known for its commercial values as food and medicinal agents (Ajaiyeoba 2002). The husk and pods are reportedly good for feeding livestock (Obiozoba, 1998). However, the most popular form of consumption is in its traditional fermentation into dawadawa, Ogiri or iru as the case may be in Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba languages in the Northern and Southern Nigeria respectively. “Dawadawa”, “Ogiri” or “iru” is a food condiment for seasoning traditional soups (Campbell-Plat 1980). Processing of African Locust bean seeds into fermented forms for food condiments follows the flow chart in (Figure 1).

The traditional practices of processing fermented locust beans indigenously are practiced by the aged especially women in rural communities. The preference of calabash as fermentation containers during “iru” processing has stuck as a tradition and attempt to in-cooperate other types of containers for fermentation has met stiff opposition. But due to increase in demand for this important food product arising from population increase, other fermentation material that are available for use i.e. stainless steel and plastics alongside calabash gourd was experimented to ascertain their effects on pH and some functional properties of fermented locust beans. Other parameters considered are different fermentation times of 24 hours, 48 hours and 72 hours and different drying methods which includes sun and oven drying methods at ambient and 55°C respectively and their effects on pH and some functional properties as well.

Methodology

Fresh locust bean seeds, purchased from an open market in Idofian, Kwara State were cleaned and sorted. Approximately 5kg of the cleaned seeds were cooked to 110°C for 12 hours by adding 10 litres of water intermittently until the seed coat softened. The cooked locust bean seeds were dehulled using designed and fabricated multi-seed dehuller by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM). The dehulled seeds were steamed for 15 minutes between 40 – 45°C and left to ferment for 24, 48 and 72 hours using calabash, stainless steel and plastic as fermentation containers respectively. The fermented samples were further dried using the sun drying and oven drying method at 55°C.

Determination of Functional Properties

Determination of Bulk Density

This was determined using Giami and Bekebain (1992) method where the bulk density of flour samples were determined by weighing the sample (50g) into 100ml graduated cylinder, then tapping the bottom ten times against the palm of the hand and expressing the final volume as g/ml. Similarly this was carried out using grinded locust beans seed as sample.

Determination of Water Absorption Capacity (WAC)

The method of Abbey and Ibeh (1998) was adopted. Grounded locust bean seed samples, 1g of each treatment was weighed separately and also together with a clean dry centrifuge tube into which it was placed. Distilled water was mixed with the sample to make up 10ml of dispersion. It was then centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and the tube with its content reweighed as gram water absorbed per g of sample. The gain in mass was the WAC of the locust bean flour sample.

The determination of oil absorption capacity

This was determined using Onwuka (2005) method. 2g of grounded locust beans seed sample was mixed with 20mls of oil in a blender at high speed for 30 seconds. Samples were then allowed to stand at 30°C for 30 minutes then centrifuged at 1000rpm for 30 minutes. The volume of the supernatant in a graduated cylinder was noted. Density of water was taken to be 1g/ml and that of oil determined to be 0.93g/ml. Means of triplicate determination were reported.

Statistical Analysis

Multivariate analysis (Hotelling's trace) was used to determine the effect of fermentation time (24, 48 and 72 hours), type of fermentation container (calabash, stainless steel and plastic) and drying method (oven and sun drying method) on the functional properties of the fermented locust bean. The test was subjected into triplicates during data collection. Duncan method was used for difference in all parameters analyzed (Post Hoc Test).

Results

Fermentation time

Results presented below in Table 1, pH increased significantly with increase in fermentation time. This trend is similar to results from Iheke *et al.* (2017), for unfermented and fermented Iru. In addition, increase in pH could be indication of the formation of ammonia though the time duration of the experiment was comparably shorter than the four days fermentation that increased pH to 8.2 as obtained by Odunfa (1981) and Ojewumi *et al.* (2016) which both reported gradual increase in pH

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in the first 30 hours. Water absorption capacity increased with fermentation and dehydration. Choonhahirun (2010) reported that water absorption capacity describes flour-water association ability under limited water supply and is also used as an indication of performance in several food formations. In addition, the higher Water Absorption Capacity may be due to presence of high polar amino acids residues of proteins having high affinity for water molecules (Yusuf, 2008). The major components that enhance the WAC of flours are proteins and carbohydrates since they contain hydrophilic parts such as polar or charged side chains (Lawal and Adebowale 2004). This is also similar to WAC results with fermentation time since protein levels increases with fermentation. Low oil absorption capacity decreases with processing i.e. fermentation and dehydration, though there was no significant increase or decrease obtained from the results. Oil absorption capacity is also an important property in food formulations because oil improves the sativity, flavor and mouthful of foods (Kinsella, 1976). Obatolu *et al.* (1995) reported that OAC was attributed to physical entrapment of oil which is related to the number of non-polar side chains in the proteins that bind hydrocarbon chains of the fatty acids. Lawal (2004) attributes this behavior to the presence of non-covalent bonds such as hydrophobic interactions, electrostatic and hydrogen bonding forces that are involved in lipid-protein interactions. The major chemical component affecting OAC is protein which is composed of hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts. Non polar amino acid side chains can form hydrophobic interactions with hydrocarbon chains of lipids (Jitngarmkusol *et. al.*, 2008). The effect of fermentation time was insignificant on bulk density and oil absorption capacity.

Table 1: Effect of Fermentation Time on the pH and Some Functional Properties of the Locust Beans

FERMENATION TIME (hrs)	pH	BULK DENSITY	WAC	OIL ABSORPTION CAPACITY
24.00	5.54 ^c	0.96 ^a	1.85 ^c	1.44 ^a
48.00	6.05 ^b	0.97 ^a	2.22 ^b	1.22 ^a
72.00	6.41 ^a	0.91 ^a	2.39 ^a	1.17 ^a

WAC - Determination of Water Absorption Capacity

Fermentation Container

From Table 2, result indicates that there was significant difference of $p > 0.005$ in the pH between the fermentation containers. Suggesting that calabash could retain high temperature for enzymatic reactions than the plastic, which had a pH of 5.95. Stainless steel recorded a pH of 5.8 suggesting that the container couldn't retain enough heat to encourage enzymatic reactions. In addition, the slightly acidic pH recorded in the three containers suggests less timing to get the pH to become slightly alkaline, since Odunfa (1981) reported that fermentation takes four days to get to pH of 8.2. No

significant difference was recorded for bulk density, water absorption capacity and oil absorption capacity. The effect of fermentation containers was insignificant on bulk density, Water Absorption Capacity and Oil Absorption Capacity respectively.

Table 2: Effect of Fermentation Container on the pH and some Functional Properties of the Locust Beans.

FERMENATION MATERIAL	pH	BULK DENSITY	WAC	OIL ABSORPTION CAPACITY
Calabash	6.20 ^b	0.95 ^a	1.94 ^a	1.22 ^a
Stainless Steel	5.95 ^b	0.96 ^a	2.07 ^a	1.17 ^a
Plastic	5.85 ^c	0.93 ^a	2.03 ^a	1.44 ^a

WAC - Determination of Water Absorption Capacity

Drying Method

From Table 3, significant difference in pH between the oven dry (at 55°C) and sun dried could have been due to higher moisture loss in the oven dried sample. Bulk density, Water absorption capacity and oil absorption capacity differences were of no significance

Table 3: Effect of Drying Methods on the pH and some Functional Properties of the Locust Beans.

DRYING METHOD	pH	BULK DENSITY	WAC	OIL ABSORPTION CAPACITY
Sundried	6.40 ^a	0.92 ^a	2.14 ^a	1.30 ^a
Oven Dried	6.56 ^b	0.98 ^a	2.16 ^a	1.26 ^a

WAC - Determination of Water Absorption Capacity

Conclusion

Conclusion from the study could be summarized into the following major points:

1. pH increased with fermentation time
2. pH increased with a container that could retain heat and sustain enzymatic reactions in decreasing order of calabash > plastic > stainless steel.
3. Higher pH in oven dried samples could be as a result of moisture loss during drying.
4. Significant difference was unnoticed in Bulk density, Water absorption capacity and oil absorption capacity,

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